

SYNTAXEMIC STUDY OF MINING AND METALLURGICAL TERMS WITH A NEGATIVE AFFIX

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Abstract. The article we try to elucidate the syntaxemic relations of the syntactic compounds and the differential syntactic features which are composed of mining and metallurgical terms with the meaning of negativity. Furthermore, we analyzed their possibilities of connection with other syntaxes at the semantic field of the syntactic level.

Key words: negativity in linguistics, negative affixes, prefix, suffix, inflection, derivation, types of negative affixes, metallurgical terms, syntaxeme analysis,

Component and syntaxema, componental and junctional model.

During human lifespan people use a variety of methods to express the essence of contradiction. On the condition that, negations can be designated not in words, but in gestures, treatment, or eye contact, or even tone. Contingent on historical theory, different peoples have various approaches to this issue. The development of language demonstrates that as support of vocabulary intensifies, we may look on at poles apart manifestations of negative expressions in words. In that event, this feels necessity for a study of the category of negativity in linguistics. Principally, diverse verifications can be done in the exploration on the level of negation, in some sources it is the object of philosophy, while in other sources it is recognized as a logical point of view.

The expression of negativity in Turkic languages is demonstrated by various means, i.e. morphemes denoting negative words, negative pronouns, negative forms as well as negative conjunctions and pronouns: -ma, yuq(no), emas(not), hech ham(never), hechqachon(nevermore), hechyerda(nowhere), hechbir(nothing), na... na(neither.....nor) etc. We can be tutored in this phenomenon in some branches of linguistics. To give an example, negative pronouns and negative forms are studied in morphology, negative conjunctions in syntax, and if we focus on suffixes, word-forming affixes are studied in the "Word-formation" section of linguistics as a part of word-formation. Formative affixes are studied in the "Morphology" section of linguistics as a part of grammatical form.

By means of affixation method, it can be analysed the formation of a new negative component using word-forming negative affixes by adding to the constructive base, words belonging to the category of noun, adjective, verb and adverb are created. As a rule, grammatically affixes are broken down two types: inflectional and derivational.

Inflectional affixes can only change meaning. Among them there is a negative suffix that does not make a new lexeme, it is used the negative form of the verb as a participle almost can be expressed by all tense forms with the addition of the affix -ma:

Present: men yozmayapman-I do not write;

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Past: men yozmadim -I did not write;

Future: men yozmayman-I will not write;

If we concentrate about negative word-forming morphemes in Uzbek, it is apparent that affixes are found in word groups among adjectives and adverbs. They are be-, -siz, no- and -mas.

be- befarosat (dull), bemaza (tasteless) - adjectives, behisob (uncountable), beto'xtov (incessant) - adverbs;

no- noaktiv (inactive), noamaliy (unpractical), noaniq (unclear), noan'anaviy (unconventional) - adjectives, noiloj (perforce) - adverbs;

-mas- o'tmas (sharpless), indamas (silent), tinib-tinchimas (busy-body) - adjectives;

-siz- xabarsiz (unaware), rangsiz (colorless), savodsiz (illiterate) - adjectives, hisobsiz (uncountable), to'xtovsiz (incessant), omonsiz (unscathed) - adverbs.

The above negative suffixes are simple (inseparable from other suffixes), depending on their position with reference to the stem, they are divided into 2 types:

- Prefixes: no- noma'lum (unknown), notijorat (non-commercial),

be- beaql (ignorant), besabr (impatient);

- Suffixes: -siz tartibsiz (disorderly), mevasiz (fruitless),

-masyengilmas (invincible), suvo'tmas (waterless), so'nmas (inextinguishable).

These suffixes can be broken down: simple, derivational, compound, and even couple and repeated words to deny their meaning. For example:

simple words — behisob (innumerable), rangsiz (colorless), noiloj (unwillingly);

derivational words — ayovsiz (ruthless), sanoqsiz (innumerable);

compound words — ishyoqmas (lazy), tilbilmas (someone who doesn't know any languages)

couple and repeated words — bilinar-bilinmas (faded), non-ponsiz (breadless), bola-chaqasiz (childless).

On the other hand, negative affixes are divided into two types, according to the degree of word formation:

☐ productive (used to make many words): be-, no-, siz-

☐ non-productive (makes few words): -mas

Negative affixes play an important role in the expression of negativity in modern English and Uzbek. It should be considered that affixes are divided into prefixes and suffixes in both languages. Negative suffixes are mostly made in English - less, and in Uzbek by adding the elements -siz.

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In English, in addition to the expression -less morpheme, the noun is also an element of the adjective, which has a similar place in the Uzbek language.

umidsiz-hopeless, uysiz-homeless, maqsadsiz-aimless, harakatsiz-actionless.

If we look further at the appropriate variants of negative affixes into Uzbek to English, in compliance with the models of KayumovaMunavvarSanakulovna, It should be noted that in Uzbek language the negative element –siz that represents the negativity makes an adjective, in English it can be expressed the one using several prefixes:

|-----un+A=unaccompanied-hamrohsiz

|-----im+A=impossible-ilojsiz

|-----ill+A-logical-mantiqsiz

-siz |-----in+A=ineffective-samarasiz

|-----dis+A=dishonest-vidjonsiz

|-----non+A-nonstop-to`xtovsiz

|-----ir+A=irresponsible-ma`suliyatsiz

In Uzbek, the suffix -siz is the most widely used adjectives. Sometimes instead of the one, –be as a synonym prefix that is put to use for Persian words, and it can be given to English by the following prefixes:

|-----im+A=impeccable-benuqson

|-----dis+A=disinterested-beg`araz

be- |-----un+A=unbalance-beqaror

|-----non+A=non-aligned-betaraf

|-----in=indifferent-beparvo

|----- A+-less=faithless-bevafo

Furthermore, the no- prefix that has the property of making an adjective adding nouns and other words creates opposite adjectives, which can be given to the English language using the following prefixes:

|-----in+A=inadmissible-nomaqbul

|-----im+A=improper-nojo`ya, noo`rin

|-----in+S=inappropriate-nomunosib

no- |-----ir+A=irregular- notug`ri

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|-----in+A=inaccurate-noto`g`ri

|-----il+A=illegal-noqonuniy

|-----dis+A=disadvantage-noustunlik

|-----non+S=nonagreement-norozilik

From the above model, it can be realized that suffixes and prefixes denoting negativity in Uzbek are given in the translation by several prefixes in addition to the suffix -less. Prefixes of negations in English, when translated into Uzbek, can be understood in other variants:

The negative prefix to the Uzbek language can be identified as follows.

|-----siz-lik (n)uncertainty-noaniqlik,

|-----be-A=unaware-bexabar

Un- |-----ma+gan-A=unannounced-kutilmagan

|-----ma+s-A=unapproachable-yetibbo`lmas

|-----siz+A=unalloyed-cheksiz

|-----no+A=unaccustomed-notanish

The above examples show that each negative affixes may not be fully compatible with each other in both languages. However, it must be mentioned that each of them must be translated into English to uzbek or into uzbek to english by consistently looking for an alternative one.

It is necessary to observe, analyze, classify the metallurgical terminology in English and Uzbek. Consequently, it is creating a demand for metallurgical terms at a time when the geological industry is developing and our country is paying great attention to this field. Inclusive of issues of terminology in English, Russian and Uzbek linguistics, the formation of terms, their linguistic features, It has been effectively studied by such scientists as H. Felber, Juan C. Sager, V.V. Vinogradov, A.A. Reformatsky, A. Khojiev, R. Doniyorov, N. Kasimov, A. Usmanov, A. Madvaliev. Additionally it should be pointed out that nowadays S.A. Abduraxmonov, F.E. Axtamov, M.S. Qayumova are conducting effective research on the field of mining and metallurgical terms.

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